

Interaction of electrochemically generated reduction products of Ornidazole with nucleic acid bases and calf thymus DNA

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5-Nitroimidazoles are important compounds used by the pharmaceutical industry with applications of combating infections caused by anaerobic bacteria, amoeba and other parasites. They are effective radiosensitizers also. Biological activity of 5-nitroimidazoles is attributed to reduction of the nitro group that equips them to enter cells of disease causing microbes by creating a concentration gradient. Several studies consider formation of the nitro radical anion ($\text{NO}_2^{\bullet-}$) and other reduction products essential for their activity. While inside the cell, these reduction products interact with DNA, disrupting or breaking strands and causing cell death. To look into this aspect, Ornidazole [1-chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-nitro-1H-imidazole-1-yl)propan-2-ol], belonging to 5-nitroimidazoles was selected. Reduction products of Ornidazole was generated by an electrochemical reduction of it at a constant potential (-0.827 V) determined using cyclic voltammetry. Purine and pyrimidine bases as well as calf thymus DNA were kept in the immediate vicinity of generated reduction products. The amount of reduction products generated depended upon the time for which Ornidazole was subjected to reduction at the constant potential. Reaction of the generated reduction products with purine or pyrimidine bases was followed using HPLC while the amount of calf thymus DNA that was not modified was determined by treating the DNA with ethidium bromide and recording its fluorescence following an excitation at 510 nm. The study revealed damage and/or modification caused to different targets by the generated reduction product of Ornidazole. The damage caused to purine and pyrimidine bases was then correlated with that observed on calf thymus DNA.

Keywords: Ornidazole, adenine, thymine, cytosine, guanine, calf thymus DNA.

Introduction

Nitroimidazoles are a very useful class of drugs important for a number of reasons. They are extensively used for problems pertaining to anaerobic bacterial and parasitic infections; this being its major application¹⁻⁵. These compounds being cytotoxic to cells are also effective as chemotherapeutic agents, as radiopharmaceuticals and radiosensitizers in various forms of cancer related medical applications⁶⁻⁹. Ornidazole [1-chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-nitro-1H-imidazole-1-yl) propan-2-ol], a 5-nitroimidazole, although less popular than metronidazole or tinidazole or even misonidazole is under serious consideration these days for certain advantages it has over metronidazole, the most popular of the 5-nitroimidazoles¹⁰⁻¹³, and is slowly becoming a major component of many important pharmaceutical formulations. Through studies and application on patients, it has emerged today that reduction of the nitro group and the subsequent formation of different reduction products are crucial for their

activity^{1,7,14}. Having entered a target cell by diffusion, antimicrobial activity of nitroimidazoles depend upon the reduction of the nitro group to a nitro radical-anion and/or other potentially active compounds that includes the nitroso and the hydroxylamine derivatives^{1,14}. Reduction products of nitroimidazoles are damaging to various macromolecules including DNA, bringing about their degradation through strand modification^{1,7,14}. Almost all nitroimidazoles are selectively toxic to different micro-organisms who actually provide them the desired redox potential so that the electron transport process can occur uninterrupted and if sufficiently negative, it is able to reduce the nitro group of the nitroimidazole moiety, in the process inviting its own death. By and large, this has been the mechanism of activity of the nitroimidazoles and pharmaceutical companies have exploited this aspect to their advantage. For nitroimidazoles acting as radio-pharmaceuticals or radiosensitizers, the cause for action is more or less the same, the only difference being

that in this form of application, the nitro-radical anion ($R\text{-NO}_2^{\bullet-}$) probably has a larger role than other reduction products⁶⁻⁹; R signifies the portion of a nitroimidazole other than the nitro group. Although, there is some work in the literature on modification of DNA due to nitroimidazoles, there is lot of scope for further investigative work^{15,16}. Here, in this communication, we look at the aspect as to how the nitro radical anion or other reduction products generated inside a cell that provide these molecules with the appropriate reduction potential, interact with nucleic acid bases or DNA. In our case, the reduction potential was provided to our chosen nitroimidazole (Ornidazole) by an electrochemical method using glassy carbon electrode, where, in the immediate vicinity of reduction products of the molecule four different nucleic acid bases (taken one at a time) or calf thymus DNA was kept. The reduction products bring about a damage of the biological target which was followed with the help of suitable experimental techniques. Hence, to be able to do this work, it was necessary to identify the reduction potential of Ornidazole which was done in aqueous medium prior to start of actual experiments.

Experimental

Materials used:

Ornidazole was purchased from Sigma Aldrich and purified by re-crystallization from alcohol. NaCl, NaNO₃, KCl (all AR grade) were purchased from E. Merck, India. Triple distilled water was used for preparing aqueous solutions. Calf thymus DNA was purchased from Sisco Research Laboratory, India and dissolved in triple distilled water. Concentration of DNA was determined in aqueous solution using a molar extinction coefficient of 6600 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 260 nm. Absorbance was also measured at 280 nm and A_{260}/A_{280} was found out. It being in the range of 1.8 to 1.9, the DNA was considered ready for use requiring no further purification. Quality of calf thymus DNA was also verified using circular dichroism (CD) recorded at 260 nm using a CD spectropolarimeter (J815, JASCO, Japan).

Electrochemical behavior of Ornidazole:

Cyclic voltammetry was performed on Ornidazole to study its electrochemical behavior in aqueous solution using 0.12 M KCl as supporting electrolyte (Fig. 1). Before each electrochemical experiment, solutions were de-aerated with the help of Argon for 30 min. Electrochemical measurements were

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 1 mM Ornidazole showing a single step one electron reduction in 0.12 M KCl in an aqueous 20% methanol solution on a glassy carbon electrode; Scan rate being 100 mV/s.

made in a 50 ml electrochemical cell. The cathodic peak current (I_{pc}) in amperes at -0.827 V (Fig. 2) was plotted against square root of potential sweep rate ($v^{1/2}$) to see if the process was diffusion controlled; the same being an essential criteria for the actual experiment to be performed.

Fig. 2. Plot of cathodic peak current (I_{pc}) vs square root of scan rate (v) for the four-electron reduction of Ornidazole in aqueous solution at a potential of -0.827V and pH ~7.2.

Interaction of reduction products of Ornidazole with biological targets:

Reduction of Ornidazole was achieved by maintaining a glassy carbon electrode at its previously determined reduction potential in aqueous medium. The generated reduction

products were allowed to react with nucleic acid bases or calf thymus DNA kept in its immediate vicinity. The amount of each nucleic acid base remaining after the experiment was determined with the help of HPLC (Shimadzu) using a C-18 column and 5% aqueous methanol as the mobile phase in case of thymine, cytosine and adenine and 40% aqueous methanol for guanine. The amount of calf thymus DNA not modified following interaction with the generated reduction products of Ornidazole was determined by treating such DNA with ethidium bromide, an established intercalator of DNA and reported to cause an increase in fluorescence upon interaction with DNA, by recording its fluorescence¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Fluorescence was recorded on a RF-530 IPC Spectrofluorophotometer, Shimadzu.

Results and discussion

In aprotic media, the nitro group of 5-nitroimidazoles undergoes a reversible one-electron reduction to a nitro radical anion followed by a three-electron reduction to hydroxylamine derivatives. The first step is reversible, while the second involving three electrons is not, established through studies on metronidazole¹⁶. However, in aqueous solution these two steps are not realized separately and a single step four electron reduction is observed^{15,16}.

As shown in Fig. 1, we too obtained a one-step four electron reduction of Ornidazole to hydroxylamine derivatives i.e. RNHOH. As identified through previous studies, there is scope for an interaction of the various reduction products of nitroimidazole, whereby RNHOH could participate in chemical reactions subsequent to its electrochemical generation. We made an attempt through this study to realize the interaction of such reduction products of Ornidazole formed in solution, with different nucleic acid bases and DNA. This was done to investigate the interaction of the reduction products (here generated electrochemically) with DNA, once this category of drugs enter the cells of a biological target that it ultimately kills. Ornidazole, a molecule used in different pharmaceutical formulations⁹⁻¹³ have significant medicinal applications and since drug activity essentially depends on reduction products it was chosen with a purpose for this investigation. As mentioned already reduction of Ornidazole in

aqueous solution was done by maintaining a glassy carbon electrode at the determined reduction potential of it, as identified prior to start of the actual experiment (Fig. 1). Nucleic acid bases or DNA with which we wanted the reduction products generated from Ornidazole to interact were taken in an electrochemical cell along with Ornidazole and the previously determined reduction potential was applied. The reduction products of Ornidazole interact with a biological target kept in the immediate vicinity of its generation, taken one at a time in the experiments we performed. There exists the possibility of the appearance of $\text{R-NO}_2^{\bullet-}$ by comproportionation of RNO_2 and RNHOH and subsequent disappearance by disproportionation^{14,16}. However, if there be a substrate, with which $\text{R-NO}_2^{\bullet-}$ could interact then as normally expected, the possibility of disproportionation decreases drastically unless the rate of disproportionation is significantly greater than the reaction of $\text{R-NO}_2^{\bullet-}$ with any biological target which is usually not the case since the concentration of a biological target taken in the experiment is a lot higher than the electrochemically reducible substance (here Ornidazole)¹⁶.

HPLC profiles of a pyrimidine base cytosine and purine base adenine following their damage after subjecting them to interaction with the reduction products of Ornidazole is shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. Figures S1 and S2 (in Supplementary Information) are those for thymine and guanine respectively.

The figures indicate as time for electrochemical reduction of Ornidazole was gradually increased during experiment, a distinct change was observed in the area obtained for the eluting nucleic acid base. Base damage was subsequently identified by plotting percentage nucleic acid base remaining against the time provided to generate reduction products of Ornidazole using a glassy carbon electrode maintained at -0.827 V in aqueous solution at pH 7.2. Fig. 5 shows this for cytosine and adenine while Fig. S3 (in Supplementary Information) is for thymine and guanine.

A similar study as described above was also performed keeping calf thymus DNA in the immediate vicinity of the generated reduction products of Ornidazole using glassy carbon electrode maintained at -0.827 V in aqueous solution at pH 7.2. The only difference for the study with DNA was that slightly longer times were used in applying the reduction potential so that more reduction products of

Fig. 3. HPLC chromatograms recorded at 254 nm for 1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} cytosine solution that was subjected to a potential of -0.827 V in presence of 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} Ornidazole under Ar saturated conditions. A-F indicates the time in minutes that the potential was applied on the solution: (A) 0 min, (B) 2 min, (C) 4 min, (D) 6 min, (E) 8 min, (F) 10 min.

Fig. 4. HPLC chromatograms recorded at 254 nm for 1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} adenine solution that was subjected to a potential of -0.827 V in presence of 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} Ornidazole under Ar saturated conditions. A-F indicates the time in minutes that the potential was applied on the solution: (A) 0 min, (B) 2 min, (C) 4 min, (D) 6 min, (E) 8 min, (F) 10 min.

Fig. 5. Nucleic acid base degradation plots for cytosine and adenine followed by HPLC at 254 nm after the compounds were subjected to a potential of -0.827 V under Ar saturated conditions in the absence and presence of a sensitizer (Ornidazole): [Ornidazole] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} . Black line indicates the absence of Ornidazole while the red line its presence.

Ornidazole could be generated thus enabling a visible recognition of the change i.e. modification caused to DNA while monitoring by the ethidium bromide-fluorescence method. Fig. 6 shows a plot of the fluorescence following interaction of such treated calf thymus DNA with ethidium bromide that was subjected to an excitation at 510 nm using a fluorescence spectrophotometer.

Table 1. Shows enhancement ratios for the damage caused to nucleic acid bases and calf thymus DNA in the presence of Ornidazole for the study described above

Compound	Target									
	Adenine		Thymine		Cytosine		Guanine		Calf thymus DNA	
	Slope in Ar saturated medium	E R	Slope in Ar saturated medium	E R	Slope in Ar saturated medium	E R	Slope in Ar saturated medium	E R	Slope in Ar saturated medium	E R
-	-0.44	-	-0.73	-	-0.31	-	-0.21	-	-0.19	-
Ornidazole	-0.74	1.68	-1.14	1.56	-0.77	2.48	-0.55	2.62	-0.52	2.74

Fig. 6. Fluorescence spectra of calf thymus DNA after treatment with ethidium bromide, following the DNA being subjected to a potential of -0.827 V in the presence of 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} Ornidazole under Ar saturated conditions. a-e indicates the time in minutes for which the potential was applied to the solution: (a) 0 min, (b) 5 min, (c) 10 min, (d) 15 min, (e) 20 min, (f) denotes the spectrum of ethidium bromide alone.

Fig. 7. A plot for calf thymus DNA modification in the absence and presence of a sensitizer (Ornidazole) after being subjected to a potential of -0.827 V under Ar saturated conditions: [Ornidazole] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} . Black line indicates the absence of Ornidazole while the red line its presence.

The modification caused to calf thymus DNA was realized by plotting the percentage of DNA remaining against the time provided to generate reduction products of Ornidazole using a glassy carbon electrode maintained at -0.827 V in aqueous solution at pH 7.2 (Fig. 7).

The outcome of the study is summarized in Table 1 provided, where we see that nucleic acid base damage inflicted

on cytosine and guanine are much higher than that caused on thymine or adenine. It is also seen that enhancement ratio obtained for cytosine and guanine in presence of Ornidazole tallies appreciably with that obtained for calf thymus DNA. Since in calf thymus DNA percentage of cytosine and guanine are much higher than that of thymine and adenine it may be said that having a prior knowledge of the damage inflicted by a molecule on a particular nucleic acid base can be an advantage as one can then have an idea as to which type of DNA is more likely to be affected the most during the action of a drug that operates by the mechanism discussed.

Conclusion

From this study it is evident that reduction products of Ornidazole modify nucleic acid bases as well as calf thymus DNA forming reactive intermediates that subsequently undergoes reactions to give different compounds as a result of which the base is eventually degraded.

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